

An introduction to the EOSC Federation

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EOSC in a nutshell

What

EOSC is the European web of FAIR data and related services for research

Research data that is easy to Find, Access, Interoperate and Reuse (FAIR)
Trusted and sustainable research outputs are available within and across scientific disciplines

Why

Unlock the full potential of research data to accelerate discoveries and innovation

How

- Ensure that Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'
- Enable the definition of standards, and the development of tools and services, to allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results
- Establish a sustainable and federated infrastructure enabling open sharing of scientific results

EOSC Federation

Data sharing in research faces **two challenges**

- 1 Ensuring **data owner control**
- 2 Providing a **secure environment** for collaboration

EOSC addresses these issues through its **federation model**

- **Complies with European regulations** such as GDPR, cybersecurity, directives and Data and AI Acts
- Provides a virtual environment where only **authenticated users** can upload high-quality, rigorously vetted data
- Offers **cross-discipline** and **cross-border** services
- Follows **robust security protocols**, ensuring that sensitive data remains protected while being available to drive scientific breakthroughs

Principles for Building the EOSC Federation

The vision for EOSC is to establish a system that enables researchers in Europe to store, share, process, analyse, and reuse FAIR research outputs—such as research data, publications, and software—across disciplines and borders.

- **System of systems approach:** Build on existing and planned infrastructures to create an interconnected ecosystem.
- **Inclusivity and accessibility:** Ensure low barriers to entry, ease of use, and broad participation.
- **Community-driven and participatory:** Engage the research community in co-creating and shaping the Federation.
- **Trust, security, and governance:** Establish clear rules, monitoring, and enforcement mechanisms to ensure a safe and reliable environment.
- **Flexibility and adaptability:** Allow for an evolutionary approach, adapting based on findings and lessons learned.
- **Autonomy and control:** Respect institutional autonomy while ensuring that data and service owners retain full control over shared resources and openness levels.
- **Broad engagement and transparency:** Keep all interested stakeholders informed and involved in key developments.

Scientific use-cases demonstrated

Multi-node scientific use cases

<u>Marine microbiomes</u>	Exploring the impact of marine microbiomes on carbon sequestration
<u>REANA</u>	Cross-node workflow for the analysis of CERN's ATLAS/CMS experiment's open data on the REANA reusable data platform
<u>Galaxy</u>	Cross-node workflow for the processing of imaging data from the environmental and life sciences using the Galaxy platform
<u>Pan-Finder</u>	The photon and neutron federated knowledge finder, PaN-Finder, an AI-enabled data search tool for navigating the large data sets of European Research Infrastructures
<u>MCVAL</u>	A prostate cancer screening tool, MCVAL, that employs multi-centric validation of AI models
<u>AMR</u>	Federated analysis of pathogen genomes

A small selection of the many use-cases being undertaken with the Nodes

Nodes engaged in 2025

 EOSC Node | PaNOSC
Physical Sciences & Engineering

 EOSC Node | Digital Twin of the Ocean
Environment

 EOSC Node | European Commission

 EOSC Node | Poland

 EOSC Node | Italy

 EOSC Node | CERN
Physical Sciences & Engineering

 EOSC Node | Slovakia

 EOSC Node | Germany

 EOSC Node | Data Terra
Environment

 EOSC Node | EUDAT
Data, Computing and Digital

 EOSC Node | Finland

 EOSC Node | SURF
The Netherlands

 EOSC Node | BBMRI-ERIC
Health & Food

 EOSC Node | Life Sciences Connect
Health & Food

Federating many service and research product catalogues - and growing!

EOSC Federation Node examples

Finland

Poland

Slovakia

Digital Twin of the Ocean

PaNOSC

EU Node

<https://eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation>

Available via the EOSC EU Node

Discover European Research Outputs

Search in all resources

Q Search

Search by Resource type

PUBLICATIONS

DATA

SOFTWARE

OTHER PRODUCTS

SERVICES

DATA SOURCES

TRAINING RESOURCES

INTEROPERABILITY GUIDELINES

[Explore the Resource Hub >](#)

Services offered by EOSC EU Node

- **Bulk Data Transfer:** Move data effortlessly to data-intensive execution environments
- **Large File Transfer:** Streamline large file transfers online with added security and integrity
- **Virtual Machines:** Design and conduct experiments with flexibility while ensuring reproducibility
- **Cloud Container Platform:** Deploy cloud-native containerised applications that can easily scale
- **Interactive Notebooks:** Create and share documents with real-time code execution
- **File Sync & Share:** Enable automatic file syncing and secure sharing across locations and teams

eosc | Tripartite

EOSC Federation Handbook

Version 2.0

Revised in
January 2026
with first wave
deployment
experiences

The EOSC Federation
Handbook has been written by
a group of **volunteers**

The Handbook provides an
overview of the organisational
and operational structure,
services and characteristics,
of the EOSC Federation

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EOSC Federation Handbook

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Thank you
for your
attention.